

Porto Angius on the Northwestern Coast of Lefkada: Cartography, Toponymy, and Spatial Transformation (17th–20th c.)

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Abstract

This study examines the historical evolution of three interconnected toponyms in northwestern Lefkada: Porto Angius, S. Mana / S. Aneta, and S. Nichita. Drawing on Venetian cartography of the 17th–18th centuries and later maps, it proposes that these names reflect layered processes of maritime memory, religious reinterpretation, and administrative transformation. The paper argues that Porto Angius preserves a pre-Ottoman nautical toponym associated with Western (including possibly Angevin) maritime activity, while S. Mana represents an Orthodox pastoral cult (likely associated with Saint Mamas), later reinterpreted under Venetian rule as S. Aneta. The emergence of S. Nichita in the early 18th century marks a new phase of coastal organization and settlement

1. Introduction

. The northwestern coast of Lefkada preserves traces of a historical toponym, “Porto Angius”, attested in early modern cartography but no longer in use today. The recognition, interpretation and eventual disappearance of this name raise important questions about the interaction between cartographic representation, local geography and patterns of economic activity.

More generally, the western coast of Lefkada presents a distinct historical landscape: sparsely populated, exposed to the open Ionian Sea and largely absent from Ottoman administrative structures¹. However, the Venetian coast consistently records a port named Porto Angius^{2 3}, adjacent to religious sites inland. This apparent contradiction raises fundamental questions about the persistence and transformation of toponyms in marginal but strategically important coastal zones⁴

The present study examines the evolution of toponyms through a comparative analysis of cartographic sources from the late 17th to the 20th century, combined with evidence from Venetian cadastral records and later maps. Particular emphasis is given to the spatial relationship between coastal landing points and inland settlements, as well as the role of religious sites in the structure of local landscapes.

¹ See Kolovos E. (2013)

² See Büsching A.F. (1776): p.273

³ See Katsardis-Hering O.(2004)

⁴ See Harley, J. B. (2001)

2. The Toponym “Porto Angius”

The harbour appears in several early modern maps with varying forms of its name. In the map of Sebastiano Alberti (1688)⁵, the designation “Porto Angius” is clearly legible. A few years later, Vincenzo Coronelli (1696)⁶ records the name in a form that may be read as either “Angius” or “Anguis,” reflecting possible uncertainty in transcription or interpretation.

Subsequent cartographic evidence, including the work of Girolamo Delanges⁷, preserves the form “Porto St Angiusi,” which likely incorporates a Greek prepositional expression (“στ’ Angiusi”) misunderstood as part of the toponym. By the 19th century, in the map of Ferdinand Aldenhoven⁸, the name appears transformed into “Porto Angello,” suggesting a reinterpretation based on the more familiar Italian word *angelo*⁹.

However, its presence in representations reflecting earlier conditions suggests that the name predates Venetian rule. Given its absence from Ottoman administrative documentation¹⁰, it is likely that Porto Angius survived as a maritime toponym, preserved within Venetian and broader Western nautical traditions^{11 12}. Its form does not conform to known Italian or Venetian lexical formations, reinforcing the view that it represents an inherited name of earlier origin, possibly pre-Ottoman and associated with Western maritime activity .

These variations indicate not the existence of multiple distinct toponyms, but rather a process of linguistic adaptation and reinterpretation of a name that was no longer transparent to its users. The persistence of the toponym across different cartographic traditions suggests that it retained practical significance within maritime networks. This is the persistence of a name despite its semantic opacity, a fact that suggests transmission within practical maritime activity rather than within administrative naming systems.

⁵ See Steiner F. (ed.) (1891): p.369

⁶ See Peacock A.C.S. (edit.) (2009): p.45

⁷ See Moschonas N. G. (1980)

⁸ See Aldenhoven, F.(1838)

⁹ The map of Ferdinand Aldenhoven (1838), one of the earliest official cartographic representations of the Kingdom of Greece, preserves earlier toponymic traditions derived from Venetian and French sources. Its depiction of the western coast of Lefkada reflects not direct field observation, but the synthesis of pre-existing cartographic material, thus offering valuable evidence for the persistence—and transformation—of names such as Porto Angius into later forms (e.g. Porto Angello)

¹⁰ See Kolovos E. (2013)

¹¹ Lane-Chapin F.(1973)

¹² Arbel, B. (2013)

Figure 1.
Comparative cartographic representations of Porto Angius (1688–1838), showing the evolution of the toponym across different forms (Angius, Anguis, Angiusi, Angello) in maps by Alberti, Coronelli, Delanges, and Aldenhoven

3. Porto Angius in the Spatial Organization of Lefkada

During the late medieval and early modern periods, the main productive zones of Lefkada were located in its mountainous interior, including settlements such as Karya and Sfakiotes. In contrast, the administrative centre of Santa Maura functioned primarily as a fortified political and military hub¹³.

Within this spatial framework, Porto Angius appears to have served as an informal maritime outlet for inland communities. Its location on the western coast, combined with its repeated appearance in nautical cartography, suggests that it was known to seafarers as a point of access to the island's interior, even if it lacked formal administrative status¹⁴.

This pattern reflects a broader duality between inland production and coastal access points, characteristic of insular environments in the Ionian Sea.

4. S. Mana: An Orthodox Pastoral Cult

Both the map of V.M. Coronelli (1696) and the map of S. Alberti (1688) record an inland site labeled S. Mana. This designation is plausibly connected with Saint Mamas, a figure widely venerated in the Orthodox tradition as protector of shepherds¹⁵.

The geographical context—mountainous terrain suitable for pastoralism—supports the interpretation of S. Mana as a pastoral settlement organized around a small rural chapel. The absence of coastal habitation at this stage is consistent with patterns of inland settlement shaped by insecurity and piracy along the western littoral¹⁶.

¹³ See Kolovos E. (2013)

¹⁴ It has been tentatively suggested that the toponym "Porto Angius" may preserve the memory of a military episode during the Angevin administration of Lefkada in the 14th century, possibly connected with the so-called "revolt of Vukentra" (See Hopf, C., (1870)). According to this hypothesis, the site may have served as a landing point for forces attempting to suppress the uprising. However, in the absence of direct documentary evidence linking the toponym to this event, such an interpretation remains speculative and is not adopted as a primary explanatory framework in the present study

¹⁵ See Kazhdan, A. (ed.) (1991): p.1277

¹⁶ See Braudel, F. (1972)

5. The Venetian Cadastre and Local Topography

The Venetian cadastral map of Caria (c. 1726), attributed to Santo Semitecolo, provides detailed insight into the inland landscape. It records the church of S. Nichita near the coastal boundary and another site identified as S. Aneta further inland.

The spatial arrangement of buildings around S. Aneta suggests the presence of a small rural settlement, likely associated with pastoral activity. The position of this site between coastal and upland zones supports the interpretation of a functional connection between maritime access and inland production.

Figure 2.

Detail from the Venetian cadastral map of Caria (c. 1726)¹⁷, showing the churches of S. Nichita and S. Aneta. Digitally enhanced for readability. The clustering of structures around S. Aneta suggests a small pastoral settlement.

¹⁷ This document can be found at the Archive Office in Lefkada.

6. The Emergence of S. Nichita

The coastal church of Agios Nikitas does not appear in 17th-century cartography and likely represents a foundation of the early Venetian period (early 18th century). Its establishment marks a shift toward controlled access to the western coastline, possibly linked to increased maritime activity and improved security conditions¹⁸.

The subsequent development of a settlement around the church indicates the gradual incorporation of the western coastal zone into the island's inhabited, economically active landscape.

7. Religious Topography and Cultural Interpretation

The same inland area named "S. Mana" in the Venetian maps around 1690, in the Venetian cadastral map of Caria (c. 1726) appears as S. Aneta. This transformation cannot be explained through direct linguistic evolution. Instead, it reflects a process of cultural and administrative reinterpretation.

As Saint Mamas was largely unknown in the Latin West, Venetian authorities or cartographers appear to have replaced the unfamiliar Orthodox dedication with a more recognizable Western equivalent. A plausible candidate is Saint Agnes, whose iconography (the lamb) resonates with pastoral symbolism¹⁹. In the Latin context, the name S. Aneta may correspond to Saint Agnes, whose iconography similarly includes a lamb. This shared symbolic attribute may have facilitated the reinterpretation of local devotional practices during the Venetian period.

Accordingly, the transition from S. Mana to S. Aneta may be understood not as translation but as functional substitution based on symbolic equivalence, reflecting the adaptive strategies of the Venetian administration in newly acquired territories²⁰. This is therefore a process of cultural substitution in which an Orthodox pastoral saint (probably Saint Mamas) was replaced by a Western saint (Saint Agnes²¹) with similar symbolic associations.

¹⁸ See Rontogiannis P. G. (1980)

¹⁹ See Caxton W. (1900): p.245

²⁰ See Arbel, B. (2013)

²¹ The conversion Agnes → Anes / Anesa → Aneta is perfectly compatible with Italian dialects (especially southern & Adriatic) Venetian script of vernacular types adaptations in non-verbal environments. See e.g. the well-known old church of «Sant'Aneta», near the Italian town of Molfetta

Figure 3.

Iconographic comparison between Saint Mamas (left) and Saint Agnes (right), both depicted holding a lamb. The shared pastoral symbolism may have contributed to the reinterpretation of local cults in rural Lefkada

8. A Three-Point System: Coast, Interior, and Memory

Taken together, the three sites form a coherent spatial and historical system:

Porto Angius: a maritime access point preserving older Western nautical memory

S. Mana / S. Aneta: an inland pastoral and religious center, subject to cultural reinterpretation

S. Nichita: a later coastal settlement reflecting new administrative and socio-economic conditions

This triad illustrates how successive historical layers—Byzantine, Angevin, Ottoman, and Venetian—are inscribed within the same micro-region through processes of continuity and reinterpretation ^{22 23}.

²² See Braudel, F. (1972)

²³ See Cosgrove, D. (2008).

9. Nineteenth-Century Transformation and Decline

The map of Marées and Partsch, edited by Wagner & Debes in Leipzig (1909) reflects a significantly altered spatial organization. The settlement of Agios Nikitas appears as an established coastal village, while inland routes converge toward it.

The map also shows two ecclesiastical sites east of the settlement, possibly preserving the memory of earlier religious locations such as S. Aneta. This suggests a process of spatial reorganization in which older pastoral zones were gradually abandoned or transformed, while religious structures were relocated to align with new routes.

The renaming of the site as Saint Anna may reflect its integration into the Orthodox ecclesiastical framework in the early 20th century.

Figure 4.

Detail from the map of Lefkada (1909) by Wagner & Debes, showing Agios Nikitas, the Lagkada stream, and inland ecclesiastical sites. The map reflects the reorientation of local spatial networks after the decline of Porto Angius. The map has been artificially colored in three areas. The area that appeared as Porto Angius on Venetian maps of the 17th and 18th centuries is colored in green. The location of the church of Saint Nichita is shown in red, and the church of Saint Aneta is shown in blue as they appear in the Venetian cadastre of 1726.

10. Conclusions

The case of northwestern Lefkada demonstrates that place names function as vehicles of historical memory shaped by mobility, administrative changes and cultural translation. Porto Angius, S. Mana / S. Aneta and S. Nichita reveal a landscape that is constantly reinterpreted by successive regimes, while maintaining structural traces of previous configurations.

The case of Porto Angius demonstrates how minor coastal toponyms, though absent from administrative records, may preserve long-term historical memory within maritime networks. It is observed how coastal place names can persist in maritime traditions even after the loss of their local functional significance. The evolution of its name reflects processes of linguistic reinterpretation, while its geographical role underlines the importance of informal coastal access points in island economies.

The integration of cartographic, cadastral and iconographic elements allows for the reconstruction of spatial transformations that connect coastal and inland environments. Porto Angius, therefore, represents not just a lost place name but a key element in the historical geography of Lefkada..

References

1. Aldenhoven, F.(1838): «Carte du Royaume de la Grèce» (s.n.) Athènes,
2. Arbel, B. (2013): «Venice’s Maritime Empire in the Early Modern Period» in E. Dursteller (ed.), «A Companion to Venetian History, 1400-1797» (Brill) Leiden, pp. 125-253
3. Braudel, F. (1972): «The Mediterranean and the Mediterranean World in the Age of Philip II. Vol. I.» (Fontana/Collins) London
4. Büsching, A.F. (1776): “Nuova Geografia”, vol. 23 (Presso Antonio Zatta), Venezia
5. Caxton, W. (1900): «The golden Legend or Lives of the saints as Englished Vol. Two» (J.M. Dent &Co.) London
6. Cosgrove, D. (2008): «Geography and Vision: Seeing, Imagining and Representing the World». (I.B. Tauris) London:
7. Farmer, D. H. (2011): «The Oxford Dictionary of Saints» (Oxford University Press) Oxford
8. Harley, J. B. (2001): «The New Nature of Maps: Essays in the History of Cartography». (Johns Hopkins University Press) Baltimore
9. Hopf, C.,(1870): «Γρατιανός Ζώρζης, Αυθέντης Λευκάδος, Ιστορική Πραγματεία [Gratianus Zorzis, Authentis of Lefkada, Historical Treatise]» (translation Romanos I.A.) (Ionia) Corfu (in Greek)

10. Kazhdan, A. (ed.) (1991): «The Oxford Dictionary of Byzantium». (Oxford University Press) Oxford
11. Katsardi-Hering, O. (2004): «Η Λευκάδα στη Βενετική χαρτογραφία [Lefkada in Venetian cartography] », *Tetradia Ergassias (KNE/EIE)* 25/26, p.93-133 (in Greek)
12. Kolovos, E. (2013): «Οθωμανικές πηγές για τη νεώτερη ιστορία της Λευκάδας [Ottoman sources for the modern history of Lefkada]» (University Publications of Crete) Heraklion (in Greek)
13. Lane, F. C. (1973): «Venice: A Maritime Republic». (Johns Hopkins University Press) Baltimore
14. Moschonas, N. G. (1980): « Χειρόγραφος τοπογραφικός χάρτης Λευκάδας και Αμβρακικού του 18ου αιώνα στη Μαρκιανή Βιβλιοθήκη της Βενετίας [A handwritten topographic map of Lefkada and Amvrakikos gulf of 18th century from the Marcian Library of Venice]» *Kerkyraika Chronika* Vol.23, pp. 274-279 (in Greek)
15. Peacock, A.C.S. (ed.) (2009): «The Frontiers of the Ottoman World (Proceedings of the British Academy: Themed volumes of essays in the humanities and social sciences, 156) » (Cambridge University Press) Cambridge
16. Rontogiannis, P. G. (1980): «Ιστορία της Νήσου Λευκάδος. Τόμος Α' [History of the Island of Lefkada. 1st volume] » (Eteria Lefkadikon Meleton) Athens (in Greek)
17. Steiner, F. (edit.) (1891): «Verhandlungen und Wissenschaftliche Abhandlungen» (F. Steiner Verlag) Wien